

Rethinking transport

27–30 April 2020

Proceedings of 8th Transport Research Arena TRA 2020, April 27-30, 2020, Helsinki, Finland

A multi-modal approach to Traffic Management

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Abstract

Our world is changing under the influence of ever more and better services provided to everybody. This results in easier access to services and more affordable services. In the domain of Transportation, for example Mobility-as-a-Service is set to provide more, cheaper and easier to use mobility services to end user. This has great benefits in the sense of social inclusion, number of connected locations and hopefully less environmental strains as travellers can easier choose a greener option. It also provides for new approaches to Traffic Management as travellers can easier be redirected to a secondary transportation system, be it through incentives or sheer cheaper or faster modes of transport. This enables Traffic Managers to spread travel demand and balance the various transportation networks to an optimum. This paper describes the interaction between various stakeholders and the end user through the deployment of Social Traffic Management®.

Keywords:

SOCIAL TRAFFIC MANAGEMENT®, MOBILITY-AS-A-SERVICE, IMPACT AWARE ROUTING

Introduction

The social community approach presented by this paper offers a personalized traffic information service and traffic management platform, which is based on mainstream social media, and aims to best match demand and supply with the intent to improve travellers' comfort and ease road congestion. Social Traffic Management® is also intended as a tool supporting road authorities and mobility service providers in their service provisioning interaction with travellers. The platform has a multi-modal approach, including Public Transport, bike or taxi services, to best match demand to capacity and user preferences.

1. Approach

One of the tools within Social Traffic Management®[1] is to actively connect to target groups, often through existing social media communities and platforms, which are generally related to a specific location or event. This approach was successfully applied at the International Hansadays in Kampen, and the ArenaPoort area in Amsterdam which includes a football stadium (Johan Cruyff Arena) and several concert venues. The area accommodates up to and beyond 80.000 visitors at peak times when several large audience events take place simultaneous. In this case the relevant community consists of concert visitors, which could be easily identified through social media "posts" and "likes" related to the concert or identified during their on-line ticket purchase through the concert organizer. By acting as a service provider towards these visitors, they were pro-actively informed about travel options, traffic flow, accessibility, timetables, parking options, etc. Reversely, visitors were able to contact the service centre by using their preferred social media channel (e.g. Whatsapp, Facebook Messenger, Twitter, etc.) to ask for specific information related to their mobility needs. No additional app download is ever required. For these deployments of Social Traffic Management we collaborated with Livecrowd.

Figure 1 – Social Traffic Management®

2. Traveller experience

The Social Traffic Management® platform, in essence, is a premium personal assistant right in your smartphone or on your computer. Its core purpose is to take the visitors of an event, exhibition or even city on a journey towards the event and guide them safely home afterwards. By doing so, Social Traffic Management® generates optimal travel experiences at events. This is of interest to the event

host (better travel experience makes for a higher event attraction) and the local governments (less traffic disruption for all traffic). For this an event community is targeted and interacted with. This community can use the platform for all their questions, about event specifics such as the location of entrances, Kiss&Ride locations, what is the quickest route to the parking location with parking space upon my arrival and near entrance C? Where can I eat near the event, so I can leave/travel early to be on time. It does this through existing, commonly used social media channels and communication apps. It mainly uses Whatsapp, Twitter, Facebook. Customers already use these channels, making access to our Social Traffic Management® service hassle free. Our service team is in constant contact with event organizers, the venue owner, road authorities even the police, ensuring that every question can be answered quickly and with an answer that is valid for the current or upcoming situation.

3. Cross Domain orientation

Traditional Traffic Management is done from a Traffic Management Centre using a huge number of monitors, incoming data and a variety of systems to communicate to the end user e.g. the road user. On a higher-level Traffic Management strategies are developed beforehand. Building coping strategies for day-to-day situations and extraordinary events where a lot of traffic is expected within an area. And then there are the heroes of Traffic Management, the road marshals, who manage traffic incidents on the spot, with fast responses and practical solutions on the road side.

Traffic Management is thus done within the domain of asphalt roads with cars on them. There is nothing wrong with this, as this is where the core of traffic delays can be found. Optimizing the system while, to some extent, result in more fluent traffic.

By deploying Social Traffic Management® we try to go outside this set domain, we try to go outside the box. Social Traffic Management® creates a unique and direct communication channel with travellers. This enables the Traffic Manager to have an indication, even know, when and how many trips will be made between A and B. This future travel demand is combined with the predicted traffic state between A and B. A Traffic Manager is then able to look into the future and see where bottlenecks will occur and how these can be resolved. Due to the direct communication channel with the traveller there is a potential to influence and incentive routing choices made by the traveller. This can be done in two stages. Choosing between transport networks and route options.

Being able to offer a choice between networks is done through the Mobility-as-a-Service capabilities of the system.

4. The intermediary

Social Traffic Management® is a system, a service an effect, that enables different domains to work together. Traffic Managers and Public Transport can work in co-operation to facilitate travel demand between point A and B. One of the biggest challenges is keeping a level playing field between all parties. It can be foreseen that PT-services might want to try to fill their busses to the maximum capacity in an effort to maximise profit. This wouldn't benefit the travel experience and thus the end-user and is therefore not preferable. The same could go for owners of parking location wanting to maximize profit by filling their own locations with cars first.

The same goes for exchange of data. Data that, more than often, is sensible data from a competition perspective. All parties must feel confident that the data they share for the greater good is used for said

Figure 2 - Mobility as a Service reference architecture and Traffic management reference architecture [4]

purpose and not for competition purposes. Another factor is that in the case of demand spreading onto various networks and travel options, this should be done equally and fair. The goal is to maximise network capacity/use not pushing a specific service to the end user.

For this a trusted third party, an intermediary, will monitor the network(s), access the impact based on the service offerings, spread the travel demand onto the various service offerings and monitor the effect and adapt where possible. This principal is being further development with a number of projects.

5. Relation to Traffic Management Centres – Socrates 2.0 Project[5]

Slotting traffic to give road users a specific arrival time can be used for everyday commutes. For example, travellers towards large offices or industrial areas can be given timed slots to arrive at a given time. Smart Routing can be used to reduce pollution in certain areas. Avoid noise pollution or

create a safer environment near schools. Within Socrates, all stakeholders that play a part in informing the end users come together to establish the best possible information and routing to be provided to the end-users. The cooperation as several forms[2,3] but in the end is always targeting the most optimal situation on for the network and community. We would like to call that Impact Aware Routing.

Our platform can aid in achieving this by targeting the right community through the platform they prefer and by highlighting alternatives which are a direct benefit to the traveller and implicitly even traffic demand at the same time. Along with appointing slots to traffic, we can fill a gap in ride sharing. By knowing certain aspects of the community like where they live and work and through apps like Facebook, Twitter, Spotify and YouTube, it would even be possible to find a perfect match, e.g. to find a neighbour who works near your own office and also likes listening to Grunt Rock on your daily commute.

As an extra and very effective tool, the platform has access to Google Maps and Waze which offers insights in traffic flows from app data and can alter traffic maps in real-time. In doing so all road users navigating with Google Maps and/or Waze will get real-time routing advice based on current events on the road network around the event, or along the route towards the venue. In doing so traffic flow can be managed to reach the most suitable parking location for their origin and with available space.

Figure 3 - Interaction between service providers and traffic centres within project SOCRATES2.0

doing so, we are able to manage the road network in an optimal way, with road users who receive a personal routing advice which they will follow for their own benefit. This is an advantage for the road operators, as they can focus their attention to all other traffic. And the visitors will experience an almost VIP-like, personal service.

6. Relation to Mobility-as-a-Service (MaaS) – H2020 MyCorridor[6]

MyCorridor’s mission is to facilitate sustainable travel in urban and interurban areas and across borders by replacing private vehicle ownership by private vehicle use, as just one element in an integrated/multi-modal MaaS chain, through the provision of an innovative platform, based on mature ITS technology, that will combine connected traffic management and multi modal services and thus facilitate modal shift. It will propose a technological and business MaaS solution, which will cater for interoperability, open

data sharing, as well as tackling the legislative, business related and travel-behaviour adaptation barriers, enabling the emergence of a new business actor across Europe; the one of a Mobility Services

Aggregator. It enables travellers to use all modalities using one account with one token or with one fixed monthly subscription fee. MyCorridor has the aim to develop the necessary means that connects all current and up-coming modalities from where any MaaS operator can present these modality options (or a chosen selection) to its customer. The customer can choose his preferred modality, pays for it with a universally accepted token and be on the way in seconds.

Within this concept, our Social Traffic Management® platform will have a role as a customer service, i.e. a personal assistant which suggests upon request the most suitable mode of travel, based on expected traffic conditions, user preferences, weather, parking availability at the destination, traffic management schemes, etc. Whether it be by car, train, bike, bus, carpooling, taxi or any given combination, we will inform based on the best option for the individual, given present constraints, will book those options and will manage all financial transactions needed to be able to choose all transportation modes. Our vision is that the user should be able to use the transport service of his choice, be it Uber, SnappCarr, a standard taxi, GreenWheels or Waze Carpool, and when selected it should be available.

Within the MyCorridor project it is our goal to blend the best of Social Traffic Management® with MaaS and to establish an open platform and a one-stop-shop to every mobility service known at this moment, or starting at some point in the future can connect to. It should be possible to check, book and pay the desired service through existing channels (e.g. Facebook, Whatsapp, Twitter) and unlock the service 'capsule' too (unlock bike, unlock GreenWheels vehicle, check-in at public transport, etc.). All the user would need is their phone with Whatsapp, Facebook or whichever social media/chat platform they like most.

7. MyCorridor Pilot – Amsterdam

The MyCorridor project consists of 6 pilot sites in which and between which Mobility is provided as a Service. The pilots have a local, urban, interurban and cross-border scope. This means that the MaaS products will be available for a large region and will be available throughout European Countries.

The Amsterdam pilot will be focusing on urban and interurban aspects and also on cross-border travel. The pilots aim will be creating a hassle-free, impact driven, integrated, door-to-door journey. Meaning that we will provide the best routing option through any modality taking into account current and projected traffic states, personal preference of the end-user, and what the best mode of transport should be for the system of travel infrastructure as a whole. Thus, satisfying travel and road authority needs.

To achieve this we will be relying on the principals of Traffic Management 2.0 (TM2.0) and also the practical approach of TM2.0 within the CEF project, Socrates2.0.

The pilot will be set around a large event in the area around the Johan Cruiff Arena in. The pilot will focus on using the Social Traffic Management® approach in relation to the MaaS concept being tested and developed in MyCorridor. By doing so, users have a one-stop shop available on his phone/laptop/computer through which they have access to;

- Event information
- Area Information
- Travel Information
- Travel ‘Ticketing’

In this way Social Traffic Management® will be able to inform users on their best travel options and also provide users with the needed tickets. For this users will be able to pay for the tickets through the platform of choice (i.e. WhatsApp, Facebook, Twitter). In return users will receive a personalized travel advise and information including all tickets and if needed reservations (i.e. parking, seating, etc).

For the Amsterdam pilot this will be possible through QR-codes for most travel modes. We envision to also include a wireless payment/access integration through NFC. The goal will always be to let users use the system without the need for extra physical cards or additional apps/software. For an example with the use of Whatsapp.

Figure 4 – Social Traffic Management® interaction with a traveller to plan and book a trip including ticketing

8. MaTmEx

Inspired by the projects mentioned above, we started another project last year, in which we are developing a Mobility as a Service (MaaS) and Traffic management Exchange platform (MaTmEx). The goal is to bridge the gap between collective traffic information (road authorities) and individual traffic information (service providers) by developing a platform where both sides can provide valuable input and collect valuable information to improve their own processes and business.

The Traffic management platform is a traffic management tool in which road authorities and transport providers can add actual traffic management scenarios to achieve a change in travel behaviour. During events, for example, traffic management measures activated by road authorities, such as road closures and alternative routes, are shared with service providers via this platform. Service providers can provide feedback via this platform on the number of people who have followed an alternative route or have avoided a certain area.

The MaaS platform integrates the information provided by the traffic management platform with available transport modes. When a traveller inserts his or her destination, then the MaaS platform calculates available travel routes, transport modes and even the price of their travel.

9. Conclusions

Social Traffic Management® offers a new approach to traffic management based on social media. In 2016 and 2017 the approach was successfully applied at multiple large-scale events and was selected as the primary instrument to inform travellers about travel options during a large road maintenance and reconstruction project running until 2022. For 2019 Social Traffic Management® is planned to also include MaaS application. In this way Social Traffic Management® can offer a new set of tooling for Road Operators to extend their traffic management effects into and with the use of new mobility domains.

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